

Logo Colours for Leading Companies in the UK and Japan

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Abstract

A survey of logo colours was conducted using UK's FTSE-100 data from 1984 to 2007 and Japan's Tokyo Stock Exchange Market data in 2005. The results show that blue, red, white and black are the most popular for both UK and Japanese logos. Nevertheless, a number of colours show different preferences in the two countries. For instance, although white was popular (19%) for the commercial sector "Oil & Gas" in the UK, it was never used as a logo colour in Japan for this sector. A visual assessment was conducted to investigate whether there was any links between logo colour and commercial sector. The experimental results show that the colours that people might think of in association with specific commercial sectors may differ from the colours actually used in existing company logos.

Conference theme: Values and Culture

Keywords: logo, colour, cross-cultural study

Introduction

A key aspect of branding, logo is considered a critical in-store recognition aid, speeding selection of the preferred product (Berry, 1989; Morrow, 1992). It is a symbolic embodiment of all information connected to the products and services to create associations and expectations around it. The main goal of a logo is to enhance awareness about the brand and to build a beneficial image (Hem and Iversen, 2004). Good logos are recognisable and familiar, should be able to elicit a consensually held meaning in the target market, and evoke positive affect (Henderson and Cote, 1998).

As an integral component to logo design, colour is crucial to brand recognition and can effectively communicate the essence of a company's products and services to its staff and customers. Colour also plays a substantial role in creating a desired affect or image (Kobayashi, 1981) and can lead to the preference for the products or services on both local and global markets. The issues of colour logo design thus include not only semantic associations (Sato *et al.*, 2000; Ou *et al.*, 2004a-b), colour preferences (Ou *et al.*, 2004c) and harmony (Ou and Luo, 2006), but also the effect of culture on colour (Ou *et al.*, 2005) and marketing.

The present study investigates the use of colour in company logos for various commercial sectors in the UK and Japan, in order to see whether and how logo colours are influenced by different sectors or by countries. To achieve this, two stages of investigations were undertaken: (a) a survey of logo colours on current stock exchange markets and (b) a visual assessment on congruity between logo colour and commercial sector.

A Logo Survey

To see whether there is any trend of colour usage for company logos, two logo datasets were collected: one from companies on the FTSE-100 list (UK) from 1984 to 2007 and the other from those on the first division of Tokyo Stock Exchange Market (Japan) in 2005. The CIE colour specifications (CIE, 2004), such as CIELAB hue angle, chroma and lightness (Hunt, 1998), for each logo colour were determined as colour standards using a tele-spectroradiometer.

A total of 353 UK companies have been on the FTSE-100 list since 1984, all of which are included in this study. The 353 companies can be divided into 10 commercial sectors. Definitions of the 10 sectors are summarised in Table 1.

The first division of Tokyo Stock Exchange Market, on the other hand, divides all Japanese leading companies into 28 sectors, as shown in Table 2. There are currently 1311 companies on the list in 2005, all of which were studied in this work.

These logo colours were classified into Berlin and Kay's 11 basic colour names (1969): white, grey, black, brown, pink, yellow, red, orange, green, blue and purple. The classification was undertaken using modified CIELAB definitions by Lin *et al.* (2001), as summarised in Table 3.

Commercial Sector		Subsector
U1.	Oil & Gas	Oil & gas producers, oil equipment, services and distribution
U2.	Basic Materials	Chemicals, forestry & paper, industrial metals and mining
U3.	Industrials	Construction & materials, aerospace & defence, general industrials, electronic & electrical equipment, industrial engineering, industrial transportation and support services
U4.	Consumer Goods	Automobiles & parts, beverages, food producers, household goods, leisure goods, personal goods and tobacco
U5.	Health Care	Health care equipment & services, pharmaceuticals and biotechnology
U6.	Consumer Services	Food & drug retailers, general retailers, media, travel & leisure
U7.	Telecommunications	Fixed line telecommunications and mobile telecommunications
U8.	Utilities	Electricity, gas, water and multi-utilities
U9.	Financials	Banks, non-life insurance, life insurance, real estate, general financial, equity investment instruments and non-equity investment instruments
U10.	Technology	Software & computer services, technology hardware and equipment

Table 1. UK commercial sectors defined by the Industry Classification Benchmark (ICB)

Commercial Sector		Japanese Translations
J1.	Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries	農林水産
J2.	Mining	鉱業
J3.	Construction	建設
J4.	Food	食品
J5.	Fiber and Textile	繊維
J6.	Pulp and paper	パルプ・紙
J7.	Chemistry	科学
J8.	Oil and Coal	石油・石炭
J9.	Rubber goods	ゴム製品
J10.	Ceramic	窯業
J11.	Steel	鉄鋼
J12.	Nonferrous metal	非鉄金属
J13.	Metal	金属製品
J14.	Machine	機械
J15.	Electric products	電気機器
J16.	Transport machine	輸送用機器
J17.	Precision instrument	精密機器
J18.	Other manufacturing	その他製造
J19.	Commerce	商法
J20.	Money, Banking and Assurance	金融保険
J21.	Real estate	不動産
J22.	Land transportation	陸運
J23.	Marine transportation	海運
J24.	Air transportation	空運
J25.	Warehouse and carrier	倉庫運輸
J26.	Information and communication service	情報通信
J27.	Electricity and Gas	電気・ガス
J28.	Service	サービス

Table 2. Japanese commercial sectors for the first division of Tokyo Stock Exchange Market

	L*		C* _{ab}		h _{ab}	
	≤	>	≤	>	≤	>
White	100	90	5	0	—	—
Grey	90	40	5	0	—	—
Black	40	0	5	0	—	—
Brown	60	29	44	5	25	80
Pink	100	60	50	5	340	65
Yellow	100	71	—	—	66	100
Red	—	—	—	—	10	40
Orange	—	—	—	—	40	66
Green	—	—	—	—	66	196
Blue	—	—	—	—	196	290
Purple	—	—	—	—	290	10

Table 3. Lin *et al.*'s (2001) colour naming model in terms of L*, C*_{ab} and h_{ab}, which represent CIE lightness, CIELAB chroma and hue angle, respectively.

As a result, the FTSE-100 data were found to show a consistent trend for UK logo colours throughout the time since 1984. Figures 1 (a) and (b) show percentage of colour occurrence in these logos, for dominant colour (i.e. the colour that occupies the largest area in a logo) and support colours, respectively. As shown in Figure 1 (a), blue was found to be the most widely used dominant colour, making up the largest proportion (49%), followed by red (19%), black (16%) and green (7%).

For support colours, white was found to be the most widely for the past 24 years, with a percentage of 36%, followed by yellow (15%), green (13%), blue (10%), orange (8%) and red (7%), as shown in Figure 1 (b).

Figure 2 (a) shows the average results of colour usage since 1984 including both dominant and support colours. The most widely used logo colour was found to be blue, with a percentage of 32% among other colours, followed by white (20%), red (12%), black (10%) and green (9%).

To compare the colour usage in logos between UK and Japan, we calculated the occurrence of colours in Japanese logos. Figure 2 (b) shows the calculation results: blue being the most popular logo colour (32%), followed by red (20%), white (15%), black (14%) and green (7%).

According to the results shown in Figures 2 (a) and (b), great similarity was found for the two countries – blue, red, white and black being the most widely used logo colours for both the UK and Japan. Nevertheless, significant differences can still be found. For example, white was found more widely used in the UK (20%) than in Japan (15%); red and black were both found more widely used in Japanese logos (red 20% and black 14%) than in UK logos (red 12% and black 10%).

(a)

(b)

Figure 1. Occurrence of (a) dominant and (b) support colours in UK logos from 1984 to 2007

(a)

(b)

Figure 2. Percentage of colours used in (a) UK and (b) Japanese logos

To compare the colour usage in logos for each commercial sector between UK and Japan, we divided both UK and Japanese logos into 10 commercial sectors as defined by the Industry Classification Benchmark (see Table 1). Note that these 10 sectors are for UK companies. For Japanese companies, however, there are 28 commercial sectors, as shown in Table 2. To compare logo colours between the two countries, we managed to merge the 28 Japanese categories into the 10 UK sectors, as summarised in Table 4. Note this was a difficult merger and that there was no perfect match between the two systems. For instance, we did not find any Japanese category that directly matches the “Health Care” sector as defined in the UK.

Figures 3 (a) and (b) show a breakdown of colour occurrence into the 10 sectors for companies in the UK and Japan, respectively. From these diagrams, different patterns of colour usage can be found. First, there are greater variations of colour usage in the 10 commercial sectors for UK companies than Japanese companies. For example, for Japanese companies (except those in “Oil & Gas” and “Utilities” sectors), the most widely used logo colours were always blue, red, white and black; for UK companies, however, colour usage was found to be different from sector to sector.

For comparisons of logo colours in each commercial sector, the following shows the most significant differences between the UK and Japan:

- Oil & Gas – in the UK, green (22%), yellow (20%), red (19%) and white (19%) were most widely used. In Japan, however, logos of this sector were dominated by red (42%), which was followed by blue (21%), black (16%) and yellow (16%). Note that although white was popular for use in UK logos, it was never used as a logo colour in Japan for this sector. Note also that although green was popular for this sector in the UK, it was not as widely used (5%) in Japan.
- Utilities – in the UK, the most widely used logo colours in this sector were blue (36%) and white (22%) and green (17%), while in Japan the most popular colours were black (34%), blue (29%) and red (20%). Note that although white was popular for use in UK logos, it was never used for this sector in Japan.
- Technology – the UK logos in this sector were dominated by blue (42%), black (19%) and yellow (12%), while in Japan the most widely used colours were blue (37%), white (18%), black (16%) and red (16%). Note that although yellow was popular for use in UK logos, yellow was rarely used (3%) for this sector in Japan.

- Industrial – the UK logos in this sector were dominated by blue (30%) and white (27%), while in Japan the most widely used colours were blue (37%), followed by red (19%), black (16%) and white (14%).

What follows shows comparison results about general usage of colour:

- Blue – while always popular for all commercial sectors in Japanese logos (more than 20%), blue was not as popular in the UK for sectors “Oil & Gas” (11%) and “Consumer Goods” (15%).
- Red – in Japan, red was popular for all commercial sectors, especially for “Oil & Gas” (42%). However, red was found to have wide variations between different commercial sectors in the UK. Notably, red was found rarely used as a logo colour for “Technology” (3%).
- White – in the UK, white has been a popular logo colour for all commercial sectors, but in Japan white was never used for sectors “Oil & Gas” and “Utilities”.
- Black – in Japan, black was popular for all commercial sectors, especially for “Utilities” (34%). In the UK, however, black had wide variations between different commercial sectors. Notably, black was rarely used for “Oil & Gas” (5%) and “Consumer Services” (6%).
- Yellow – in the UK, yellow was popular for “Oil & Gas” (20%) and “Technology” (16%), while in Japan it was popular only for “Oil & Gas” (16%).
- Green – in Japan, green was not particularly popular as a logo colour for any commercial sector, while in the UK it was found widely used for “Oil & Gas” (22%) and “Utilities” (17%).

UK	Japan
U1. Oil&Gas	J8
U2. Basic Material	J1-J2, J6-J7, J9, J12-J13
U3. Industrial	J3, J10-J11, J14, J16, J23, J25
U4. Consumer Goods	J4-J5, J18
U5. Health Care	No direct match
U6. Consumer Services	J19, J22, J24, J28
U7. Telecommunications	J26
U8. Utilities	J27
U9. Financials	J20-J21
U10. Technology	J15, J17

Table 4. Japanese commercial sectors corresponding to UK classifications

Figure 3. Logo colours (excluding white) for each commercial sector in (a) UK and (b) Japan

Visual Assessments

To see whether there is any link between logo colour and commercial sector, we conducted a psychophysical experiment in which 30 Japanese students with normal colour vision participated. The experiment was carried out in a darkened room, using a viewing cabinet with a D65 daylight simulator as the light source to present 199 colour samples individually in a random order. These colour samples included all colour chips in the Practical Colour Coordinate System (PCCS) 199c edition, each with a size of 12.0 x 17.4 cm. Each participant was asked to select one or more out of the 28 commercial sectors (see Table 2) that appeared associated with each colour presented. Figures 4 (a) and (b) show the 199 colour samples used and the experimental set-up, respectively.

The experimental results indicate that different groups of colours are associated with different commercial sectors. For instance, Figures 5 (a)-(c) show the distribution of colours in CIELAB space (CIE, 2004) that were found associated with printing, paint and paper manufacturers, respectively. The paint-related colours included red, green and blue; the printing-related colours were mainly in the areas of red and blue; the paper-related colours were more greyish than the other two colour groups.

The results were compared with real logo colours used currently by Japanese companies and significant differences were found. For instance, Figure 6 shows the distribution of colours in CIELAB space for the “Machine” sector. As shown in the diagram, the real logo colours did not contain purples, while the participants’ visual results covered the entire range of hue,

including purple. This suggests that the colours that people might think of in association with specific commercial sectors can be different from those actually used in company logos.

(a) (b)
Figure 4. Visual assessment: (a) the colour samples studied; (b) the experimental set-up.

(a) (b) (c)
Figure 5. Japanese logo colours in CIELAB space: (a) printing companies, (b) paint companies and (c) paper manufacturers. The horizontal axis (a^*) represents reddishness-greenishness; the vertical axis (b^*) represents yellowishness-bluishness.

Figure 6. Japanese logo colours in CIELAB space for the “machine” sector. Red dots represent experimental results; blue dots represent logo colours of current Japanese companies.

Summary

The aim of this study is to investigate how logo colours are affected by commercial sector and country.

For comparisons in logo colours between the UK and Japan:

- 1) The occurrence of the 11 basic colours (Berlin and Kay, 1969) in logo designs has been consistent for FTSE-100 companies since 1984. Blue has been the most widely used dominant colour (i.e. the colour occupying the largest area in a logo) and white the most widely used support colour.
- 2) Considering both dominant and support colours altogether, the most popular colour for UK logos was blue, making up 32% of all the logos, which was followed by white (20%), red (12%), black (10%) and green (9%).
- 3) In Japan, blue was the most popular logo colour (32%), followed by red (20%), white (15%), black (14%) and green (7%).
- 4) White was found more widely used in UK logos (20%) than in Japanese logos (15%).
- 5) Red and black were both found much more widely used in Japan (red 20% and black 14%) than in the UK (red 12% and black 10%).

For comparisons in each commercial sector:

- 1) Oil & Gas – although white was popular (19%) for this sector in the UK, it was never used in Japan for this sector. Note also that although green was popular (22%) for this sector in the UK, it was rarely used (5%) in Japan for this sector.
- 2) Utilities – although white was popular (22%) for this sector in the UK, it was never used in Japan for this sector.
- 3) Technology – although yellow was popular (16%) for this sector in the UK, it was rarely used (3%) in Japan for this sector.
- 4) Industrial – the UK logos were dominated by blue (30%) and white (27%), while in Japan the most widely used colours were blue (37%), followed by red (19%), black (16%) and white (14%).

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